

LiDAR Point Cloud Classification Management in SGIS v.R

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Classifications in LiDAR point cloud data play a crucial role in distinguishing various surface features, such as the ground, vegetation, buildings, or water bodies. By assigning classification codes to each point, users can easily differentiate objects within the landscape. This is especially important for tasks like generating digital elevation models (DEMs), monitoring vegetation health, analyzing urban infrastructure, and executing planning efforts in GIS environments.

With tools that allow users to manage these classifications, it becomes possible to filter and extract specific features, like isolating ground points for terrain modeling or excluding vegetation for urban planning. Proper classification ensures that subsequent analyses are more accurate and reliable. Moreover, classifications enhance visual representation, allowing different features to be displayed with unique colors or layers, simplifying data interpretation and communication.

SGIS v.R includes a built-in tool designed to help users manage classifications within a LiDAR point cloud. To access this tool, you'll need to first ensure that a LAS file has been imported into the Layers List. Once the tool is ready, it can be opened with a single click. You can find it conveniently located in the 'Element Data' toolbox on the main interface, making it easy to manage and adjust classifications as needed.

Fig. 1 To use the 'Manage Classifications' tool, first load a LAS point cloud layer into SGIS v.R. Then, click the tool located in the main 'Element Data' toolbox.

The function opens a new window with two tabs: 'Classification' and 'Tools'. The 'Classification' tab opens by default. In this tab, users can view the Classification Number, Classification Color, and a list of classification codes. Each lidar point is assigned a classification that indicates the type of object reflecting the laser pulse. Lidar points can be categorized into various classes, such as ground, vegetation, buildings, or water. These classes are represented by numeric integer codes, which follow ASPRS standards for LAS formats 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, and 1.4. All ASPRS-defined classification codes are listed in the toolbox window, with all options checked by default.

Fig. 2 The toolbox window displays all ASPRS-defined classification codes, with each option checked by default.

Fig. 3 Classification codes 1 and 2 are unchecked.

Users can easily control which class codes are visible by checking or unchecking the desired classifications. In the example shown, we've unchecked classification codes 1 and 2, representing unclassified points and ground points.

Fig. 4 Additional classes, including high vegetation, are unchecked, making the total unchecked classes: unclassified, ground, and high vegetation.

If you want to uncheck more classification codes and work with just a few, but find the graphics panel too bright, you can use the 'Change Background Color' function. This option is located in the View toolbar in the main Menu. You can choose from three background colors: white, silver, and black. For this example, we'll select black. Once clicked, the graphics panel will change instantly.

Fig. 5 The 'Change Background Color' function, located in the View toolbar of the main Menu, is used to adjust the brightness of the graphics panel.

Fig. 6 The background color of the graphics panel is changed to black using the 'Change Background Color' option from the View toolbar.

Now, moving on to the LIDAR toolbox. As mentioned earlier, all classification codes are listed and checked by default. However, the point cloud in our example doesn't include points for every classification code. Only a few of the available codes in the list are actually present in this point cloud.

Fig. 7 The LIDAR toolbox shows all default classification codes checked, though only a few are present in the example point cloud.

Instead of unchecking each classification one by one, we can save time by switching to the second tab, 'Tools'. Here, you'll find a memo box with three distinct function buttons below it. The first button, 'Get existing classification numbers,' displays all

the existing classification codes in the memo box in a clear, notepad-like format. Let's click it to proceed.

Fig. 8 The 'Tools' tab is selected, showing the memo box and the 'Get existing classification numbers' button, which displays the current classification codes in a notepad format.

All classification codes that contain points are immediately listed in a column within the memo box.

Fig.9 All existing classifications displayed in the memo box.

Fig. 10 The 'Uncheck non-existing classification' button is clicked, removing all empty classification code layers from the list.

Below the 'Get existing classification numbers' button is another function called 'Uncheck non-existing classification'. When clicked, it automatically unchecks all classification code layers that don't contain points. Let's go ahead and click it.

Fig. 11 Clicking the 'Apply Changes' button in the 'Classifications' tab updates the graphics panel with the new settings.

To apply the changes to the graphics panel, return to the 'Classifications' tab and click the 'Apply Changes' button. This will update the graphics panel with the new settings, completing the procedure.